

Preprint

Nonlinear Circuit Algebra: When your Impedances Resist Linear Analysis

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Abstract—Nonlinear system behaviour becomes increasingly more important in electrical circuit theory: As system frequencies get higher, physical linearization strategies cease to be effective. Nonlinearity is often a limiting factor of system performance, while at the same time it is often left out of thorough analysis due to the topic's perceived complexity. This work aims at giving an intuitive understanding of nonlinear electrical systems, drawing heavily from well-known principles in electrical engineering. Emphasis is put on the fact that Volterra operators are capable of approximating complex, frequency-dependent impedances, gain functions, or two-ports, be it in circuit analysis or in feedback system design, while keeping the classical notation mostly unchanged. Nonlinear circuits can become mathematical objects, making them accessible to powerful mathematical operations, similar to those that are used on complex numbers. Although designed to be simple, our notation nonetheless relies on a few computationally expensive operators. Since we want to make Volterra series useful, we aim at an easy, yet complete overview; therefore, we also include a section describing the operators in more detail. A practical example of circuit analysis is included at the end, where a class-A amplifier is analyzed, and the similarities to linear circuit theory are demonstrated.

Index Terms—Volterra Series, Two-Port Networks, Nonlinear Feedback, Nonlinear Control, Nonlinear Systems.

TODO: Weak parts are

- V-B
- VI-B - stability.
- II-D needs some polishing of notation: Pre/post arrows, and both recursive inversion equations, and order denotation on operators.
- Fixing the 2port composition equation

They will be improved in the final version.

I. INTRODUCTION

The following paper is aimed at offering a simple explanation for nonlinear effects in circuits to a broader engineering audience, already acquainted with standard circuit analysis and two-port networks. We make use of a Volterra operator algebra, whose properties [D.A. George, 1959] and, more explicitly, [George Zames, 1960] already discussed. It allows for a simple notation of nonlinear systems.

For circuit analysis, [Chua, 1979] built on their work, but he had another focus: Instead of a high-level operator approach, he calculated nonlinear transfer functions explicitly, which gave him the possibility to prove his results correct for concrete examples. However, the resulting equations, even for 2nd order, were quite complex; for engineering practice, this can be prohibitive.

Due to the simultaneous emergence of SPICE during that time, the further search for a simple analytical method likely appeared less pressing - particularly, as it promised to still require the enormous computation power associated with Volterra operators.

The historical rise in compute power ever since, and the increasing interest in nonlinear networks [Analog AI, 5G/6G distortion analysis and synthesis] change this picture. Today's and tomorrow's problems challenge circuit designers (who previously should build linear circuits from mostly linear components) with nonlinearity, and it seems that an intuitive yet thorough nonlinear circuit analysis framework is missing. This might be a reason for why X-parameters [cite], for example, were developed for the RF community; but while they do solve some important problems, others remain open. Our aim therefore is to combine and simplify the aforementioned approaches, making use of today's computation power: We propose a simple Volterra operator-based framework, which allows for nonlinear circuit analysis and connects well to linear circuit theorems, S-parameters, and other related concepts that are already familiar to engineers.

Throughout the framework, one can observe that it is structured into two layers: One, on which the operator equations representing nonlinear circuits appear strikingly similar to linear theory, and which governs the algebra for simplifying such equations; and one, in which the concrete operators are defined, and which looks more unwieldy - however, by the user, that layer seldomly has to be accessed.

This separation also allows our framework, in general, to remain domain-agnostic: We chose time-domain, but all operators can also be defined in frequency domain.

Time domain gives us the possibility to apply everything, in principle, to non-periodic and very wideband signals; this is something other descriptions, like X-Parameters [9], struggle with.

Before starting with two-port networks, we first want to show circuit analysis for one-port components, like impedances, can be performed using Volterra [18] series; and how this leads to a notation that shows remarkable similarities to the complex-valued calculus that is usually employed. In the next section, the low-level mathematical operations, needed therein, are explained in more detail.

Nonlinear two-ports are then derived as a unification of linear two-port theory (starting from ABCD parameters) and nonlinear system theory (specifically, Volterra series). Most calculations from two-port theory can very easily be adapted; only the systems and operators need to be exchanged for more powerful ones, for which we will provide a mathematical description alongside an open-source software package.

TODO: 'Describing Functions' - single nonlinear component, static nonlinearity, odd-order Schoukens PLNSS NARX Could be useful for identification. Volterra however is algebraically closed, the others are not (NARX maybe?)

II. ONE-PORT SYSTEMS (IMPEDANCES)

In this section, we show how the response of simple nonlinear networks can be calculated in terms of Volterra operator notation, and compare it to a SPICE simulation. In other notations, like [13], similar results are generally possible; but in direct comparison, the resulting equations become prohibitively complex, even for just small systems. We also discuss the occurrence of DC offsets in components, which might be present due to biasing currents or voltages.

A. Time-Domain Description of Electrical Systems

Linear impedances can be represented in time domain, instead of just frequency domain. A (discrete) complex impedance curve of $Z(j\omega)$ transforms into a real-valued, discrete time-domain representation $z(n)$ at timestep t_n .

If we apply a time series current $i(n)$ to this impedance, we get the following voltage series:

$$u(n) = z(n) * i(n) \quad (1)$$

where '*' is the convolution operator.

Fig. 1: An impedance can be transformed from (discrete) frequency domain into discrete time domain.

When working with nonlinear devices, we can simply replace the convolution with $z(n)$ by a P -th order Volterra operator. It applies a convolution, as well as nonlinear effects. Similar concepts have long been explored in frequency domain [3], [4], [15], [16]. A detailed explanation of Volterra series, and the rules that govern their basic arithmetic, can be found in section II-B:

$$u(n) = Z_P i(n) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2: Volterra impedance

Every impedance now becomes a Volterra series, giving the relationship between current and voltage at this component's pins. We can apply this to resistors, inductors, capacitors, as well as (naming a slightly harder case) to PIN diodes with slow recovery effects, self-heating and nonlinear junction capacitance. This example also implies directionality: Volterra impedances should always be marked with respect to their polarity. We do this by adding a 'V' to a resistor symbol.

B. Volterra Series as Operators, and their Basic Operations

Here, we will give the basic operators that nonlinear circuit analysis relies on. For all of them, an efficient GPU-accelerated python library is available, so they can directly be utilized for high-level circuit analysis.

The Volterra series H is an operator, which takes in a series of input values $x(n)$ and yields the output values $y(n)$. The operator's behaviour is described by its kernels h_p , which, for order p , are a p -dimensional array.

The operator can now act on a signal x , and is described by the following structure:

$$y(n) = Hx(n) = \sum_{p=0}^P H_p x(n) \quad (3)$$

with

$$H_p x(n) = \sum_{\tau_1=0}^{T_p} \dots \sum_{\tau_p=0}^{T_p} h_p(\tau_1 \dots \tau_p) \prod_{j=1}^p x(n - \tau_j) \quad (4)$$

The **composition** operation lets one Volterra operator act on another one. This is equivalent to calculating the resulting system H , when two systems $KG := K \circ G$ are chained, with

G at the input and K at the output. In time domain, this can be done using a procedure given by Kielkiewicz [8]:

$$\begin{aligned}
h_j(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_j) = & \sum_{\substack{p=1,2,\dots,j \\ \alpha_1,\dots,\alpha_n=1,\dots,j \\ \alpha_1+\dots+\alpha_n=j}} \sum_{v_1=0}^{T_p} \dots \sum_{v_p=0}^{T_p} k_p(v_1, \dots, v_p) \\
& \times g_{\alpha_1}(\tau_1 - v_1, \dots, \tau_{\alpha_1} - v_1) \\
& \times g_{\alpha_2}(\tau_{\alpha_1+1} - v_2, \dots, \tau_{\alpha_1+\alpha_2} - v_2) \\
& \times \dots \\
& \times g_{\alpha_p}(\tau_\gamma - v_p, \dots, \tau_j - v_p)
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

with $\gamma = \alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_{n-1} + 1$ and $g_0 = 0$ and $k_0 = 0$.

Volterra operators can also be **added** together. With $H = K + G$, this is done by element-wise addition of all kernels:

$$h_p(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_p) = k_p(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_p) + g_p(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_p) \quad . \tag{6}$$

Furthermore, the **inversion** operation, that will be used in the following sections, can be given in multiple forms. The original version stems from M. Schetzen [12], but we use a recursive version by [1], eq. 18, which is much simpler. Originally, it was meant for applying the inverse of a system on a signal; but noting that it is based on subtraction, addition and composition of Volterra systems (for which we all have system-level operators), the resulting Volterra kernels can be directly computed, independent of the input signal:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{(p)} &= I_{(1)} - I_{(1)}[H''_{(p)}I_{(p-1)}] \quad , \tag{7} \\
\text{with } I_{(1)} &= H_1^{-1} \quad , \\
\text{and } H''_{(p)} &= H_2 + \dots + H_p \quad ,
\end{aligned}$$

where $[\dots]_{(p)}$ represents an operator that can include **all** orders up to p , setting all higher ones to zero; and where $[\dots]_q$ specifically selects **only** the q -th order terms inside the braces, and sets all others to zero. Note that this equation is only usable for systems without offset (i.e. $h_0 = 0$). In the end of the section, we will give a workaround for cases with offset, but before that, we have to introduce a few rules about nonlinear algebra.

C. Properties of Nonlinear Algebras

Volterra operators span up three separate algebras, depending on which assumptions we make: Non-truncated series, truncated series without DC bias, and truncated series with DC bias. The first case will be discussed in detail, and we will give some additional properties of the other algebras. Note that these algebras result as a property of the systems and truncations themselves; not as a property of z-domain, frequency- or time-domain (which we focus on), or even Volterra series, for that matter. Hence, all calculations within

this algebra could be performed in either of them.

In all cases, we will see the following rules.

Composing operators is associative, meaning:

$$(AB)C = A(BC) \quad . \tag{8}$$

Furthermore, it is non-commutative:

$$B = C \tag{9}$$

$$\Rightarrow AB = AC; \quad BA = CA; \tag{10}$$

$$\text{but } AB \neq CA \quad . \tag{11}$$

And when taking sums of operators, it is right-distributive:

$$(A + B)C = AC + BC \quad ; \tag{12}$$

$$\text{but } A(B + C) \neq AB + AC \quad . \tag{13}$$

When inverting a composite Volterra operator, with series B feeding into series A , the operators exchange places, and we have

$$(AB)^{-1} = B^{-1}A^{-1} \quad . \tag{14}$$

Note: When we have structures like $A(A + B)^{-1}$, we can cancel terms both in the forward and inverse side - similar to canceling terms in a fraction. Due to the rules of the algebra, we have to cancel them from the right of our forward/inverse terms, and get:

$$AA^{-1}((A + B)A^{-1})^{-1} = (A + BA^{-1})^{-1} \quad , \tag{15}$$

which can be useful for simplifying terms, or solving for a system that should be synthesized.

These transformation rules will also apply to MIMO systems which are discussed in further sections, and govern the rearrangement of nonlinear equations. Addition and composition form an algebraic structure known as a right-distributive near-ring for Volterra operators ($V, +, \circ$), while the inversion is an antiautomorphism. A good introduction into near-rings can be found in [6] - in the preface of which, the author expresses his hope that near-rings offer a use in the generalization from linear to nonlinear cases.

In the case of truncation without DC bias, strictly speaking, we may lose algebraic closedness whenever a composition or inversion is performed. However, since the resulting truncation errors are always of order higher than P and can not leak into lower orders by composing/inverting, this leads to algebraic consistency up to order P , and often good approximations.

When we have truncation with DC bias, we lose associativity. All compositions have to be evaluated from the right to the left. In relation to circuits, this is equivalent to calculating how DC operating points propagate through the

circuit. Parentheses still take priority.

Pre-inverse and post-inverse are no longer the same, and both of them only generally preserve the correct offset when either voltage, or current at the device are zero. However, this preservation can propagate through some operations; and by a careful selection of inverse type, we can still get P-th order approximations around a DC center point, as we will discuss in the following section.

Along with those complications, we get a benefit: Both operating point, and system behaviour, can be approximated within a single calculation.

D. Inversion of systems with DC offset

The following distinction will be omitted in some other parts of this work, in order to keep the notation simple; however, we still want to discuss it here, so it can be applied when the need arises.

When a system \tilde{H} has an **offset**, we need to be very careful about composing and inverting it. First, we lose the associative property - the correct order of composition is from right to left. Only this will ensure the correct DC bias points. And while for infinite order, pre- and post-inverse are exactly equal, for a calculation at a truncated order they are not. For computing the post-inverse, the offset is shifted by applying the DC-free inverse $(H - H_0)^{-1}$ to an identity system with added constant offset (see eq. 16); we can stay in simple operator notation.

However, for the pre-inverse, dealing with the offset is not so simple. A naive approach would be to calculate the inverse of the offset-free system, yielding $I_0 = (H - H_0)_{(\infty)}^{-1}(-H_0)$, which, when applied to H , perfectly cancels the offset. However, this would require an infinite-order inversion; truncating it to order p will result in inaccurate values for I_0 . A simpler method is to compute the offset using the newton procedure, and continue the recursive inversion from there.

Below, we give the equations for both corresponding cases.

1) *Post-Inverse with DC*: The p-th order post-inverse, for which $H_{(P)}^{-1}H_{(P)} = J_{(P)}$, can easily be calculated:

$$I = (H - H_0)^{-1}(J - H_0) \quad (16)$$

J is the identity operator. The inversion operation can be calculated according to eq. 8, since the operator inside the braces has no offset.

2) *Pre-Inverse with DC*: For computing the pre-inverse, for which $H_{(P)}H_{(P)}^{-1} = J_{(P)}$, we first calculate the offset of our System. We find I_0 , so that

$$H_{(P)}I_0 = 0 \quad (17)$$

This requires

$$H_0 + H_1I_0 + H_2I_0 + \dots + H_P I_0 = 0 \quad (18)$$

This can be written as

$$h_0 + \sum_{\tau} h_1 I_0 + \sum_{\tau} h_2 I_0^2 + \dots + \sum_{\tau} h_P I_0^P = 0 \quad (19)$$

where, by $\sum_{\tau} h_p$, the sum of all kernel entries over all corresponding τ is taken. The resulting polynomial can easily be solved using a Newton procedure, yielding I_0 .

We now introduce a new System G , which resembles H with its offset cancelled:

$$G x(n) = H(x(n) + I_0) = H(J + I_0) x(n) \quad (20)$$

where J is the identity system, and we get

$$I_1 = G_1^{-1} \quad (21)$$

All higher orders $p = 2 \dots P$ are now calculated recursively:

$$I_p = -G_1^{-1} \left[G''_{(p)} I'_{(p-1)} \right]_p \quad (22)$$

$$\text{where } G''_{(p)} = G_2 + \dots + G_p \quad (23)$$

$$\text{and } I'_{(p-1)} = I_1 + \dots + I_{p-1} \quad (24)$$

Note that this bears similarity to equation 8. However, using our method, we do not get the full p-th order inversion operator $I_{(p)}$, but only its individual p-th order component I_p . For getting the full operator $I_{(P)}$, we take the sum of all I_p .

E. Using Volterra Series in Circuit Analysis

Now, we will start to see that Volterra operators can come in handy for component-level circuit analysis. Some of these basic principles have already been introduced by Chua in [4], but DC biases and advanced circuit theorems are seldomly discussed in this context.

A component's pins can be **swapped** by multiplying all even-order Volterra kernels by -1 . Odd-order terms will always behave symmetrically, so the kernels do not need to be changed if the component changes orientation.

Any physical impedance is a causal minimum-phase system [7] (although we will later see that non-causality is sometimes helpful), meaning that its inverse is also causal and stable. Consequently, for any impedance Z , a corresponding **admittance** Y can be calculated. This also extends to the nonlinear time-domain:

$$Y_P = Z_P^{-1} \Rightarrow i(n) = Y_P u(n) \quad (25)$$

For this, we can employ the well-known Pth order inversion [12] that was briefly introduced in the previous section. However, the resulting convergence radius may be limited.

TABLE I: Operation vs. center point for various operations

Operation	Equation	$u = 0$	$i = 0$
Ground truth: Impedance Z	$u = Z i$	X	X
Admittance $Y = Z^{-1}$	$i = G u$		X
Admittance $Y = Z^{-1}$	$i = G u$	X	
Parallel $Z_a Z_b = (Z_a^{-1} + Z_b^{-1})^{-1}$	$u = Z i$		X
Parallel $Z_a Z_b = (Z_a^{-1} + Z_b^{-1})^{-1}$	$u = Z i$	X	
Dual inverse $(Z^{-1})^{-1}$	$u = Z i$	X	X
Dual inverse $(Z^{-1})^{-1}$	$u = Z i$	X	X
Ground truth: Admittance Y	$i = Y u$	X	X

Impedances Z_a and Z_b can be added in **series**, by element-wise addition of all Volterra kernels $z_p(\tau_1 \dots \tau_p)$ of the corresponding impedances, going from order $p = 0 \dots P$. For calculating $Z_a + Z_b = Z_{a+b}$, we let:

$$z_{a+b,p}(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_p) = z_{a,p}(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_p) + z_{b,p}(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_p) \quad . \quad (26)$$

Nonlinear impedances can also be connected in **parallel** by adding their admittances. Using the same principle of addition, and a total of three inversions, we can compute:

$$Z_a || Z_b = (Z_a^{-1} + Z_b^{-1})^{-1} \quad . \quad (27)$$

Since we have two types of inverses, we need to make a conscious choice about which one to apply. Even when we assume that our original description of a DC-biased nonlinear impedance is exact - i.e. it is fully described by a finite-order series - its inverse will, in general, require an infinite order series in order to describe the same current/voltage relationship. Truncating the inverse will lead to a good approximation around the center point, with growing errors further away from it. It is important to note now, that the choice of inverse will simply determine which center point our series will take. Table I gives the center points for a few common applications of inverses. When the equation at both $u = 0$ and $i = 0$ is valid, it will also be valid on all other points.

Biasing of a circuit, as with a voltage or current source, can be done by describing the source as an impedance with $0th$ order kernel z_0 - another nice advantage of not restricting oneself to component models starting at first order.

With these mathematical tools, many basic operations can now be performed; this is made simple by a python-based implementation that is available for download.

Many more useful higher-level circuit-level manipulations can also be done using this description of impedances. For example, Thévenin equivalent circuits can be determined by applying just the same principles; although it should be noted that this transformation is only applicable for nonlinear circuits in which the Thévenin source is not loaded by any other

Fig. 3: Thévenin equivalent circuit with nonlinear impedances

independent signal source or variable impedance - it however works for the output shorted or open:

$$u_{th}(n) = Z_b(Z_a + Z_b)^{-1} u_s(n) \quad (28)$$

$$\text{and } Z_{th} = Z_b(Z_a + Z_b)^{-1} Z_a \quad , \quad (29)$$

which, in our notation, does not contain multiplications, but a composition (as shown in section II-B). This notation lets us keep the well-known structure of calculations with complex impedances.

In case another signal source or varying output impedances are present, we recommend describing the resistor network by a two-port system instead, as explained in the following sections. The model needs an independent input variable accounting for each source.

As is typical for most nonlinear systems, the order in which operators are arranged is very important. Equations 27 (parallel) and 29 (Thevenin) at first just appear to be the two different formulations for parallel-connected impedances (and both resemble the two well-known parallel resistor equations); however, they may not yield equal results if Z_a and Z_b are nonlinear, as discussed in section II-B.

To conclude, Volterra impedances can be connected in series or parallel. The notation stays similar to linear circuit theory; wherever a division by an impedance term occurs in the linear case, it is replaced by a composition with the impedance's inverse in the nonlinear case. They are directional devices, i.e. they have polarity. When calculating with these nonlinear operators, their associative and non-commutative properties have to be kept in mind. Volterra impedances are SISO systems: a Single Input (current) controls a Single Output (voltage).

F. A Note on Creating Component Models

A resistor with resistance R is easy to implement using Volterra series: $z_1(0) = R$; Its resistance appears in the first order kernel, all other kernel entries are 0.

When creating reactive component models, like capacitors or inductors, the procedure is not as simple. Three main points have to be traded off against each other:

- A correct amplitude and phase response;
- The component has a short causal response, and (at most)

a very short non-causal part, so it can be represented by a finite length series;

c) A good invertibility - its inverse response does not extend too far from origin, as well. This ensures that impedance can always be converted into admittance.

Point b) and c) can be restated: All poles and zeros of the components should lie between $\frac{1}{T_p} \ll P, Z \ll \frac{f_s}{2}$. If the poles lie outside this range, in many cases they can be shifted into this range with little error, as long as they are not too close to the frequency band of interest.

Note that this may require compromises. At the example of an inductor, we start by the continuous relationship $Z_{L0}(j\omega) = \frac{U(j\omega)}{I(j\omega)} = j\omega L_0$, which corresponds to $u(t) = L_0 \frac{d}{dt} i(t)$ in continuous time domain. We bring this into normalized-frequency domain first, where f_s is the sampling frequency:

$$Z_{L0}(\Omega) = j\Omega f_s L_0 \quad |_{\Omega=0\dots\pi} \quad (30)$$

$$Z_{L0}(-\Omega) = Z_{L0}^*(\Omega) \quad |_{\Omega=0\dots\pi} \quad (31)$$

This can then be discretized by evaluating Ω at frequency steps on $(-\pi\dots\pi]$. Before we transform it into time domain, we take a few additional steps:

Since the phase switches sign at the Nyquist frequency $\Omega_N = \pi$ in our normed-frequency realization, we get a sudden change in impedance. This produces a long noncausal impulse response. To mitigate that, we can add real-valued numbers around Ω_N , and apply a smoothing filter in a small range around them. This gives a gradual transition from positive-imaginary, to real, to negative-imaginary impedance (see fig. 5), and consequently a much shorter impulse response.

Furthermore, to practically realize a time-domain differentiation, we will need to allow for a noncausal response in discrete time domain (even though any physical impedance would not require that) in order to keep the phase response correct.

For better invertibility, we should also add series resistance, so that time constant $\frac{L}{R}$, corresponding to our zero, does not extend outside of our Volterra kernel length - we can then calculate the corresponding admittance with little error.

These compromises will come with the drawback that we lose accuracy at the edges of our usable frequency band ($\Omega \rightarrow 0, \Omega \rightarrow \pi$). However, we still get an accurate model throughout a quite large midband.

When these compromises can meet the component's specifications, the component can be transformed into time-domain, yielding the first-order Volterra operator Z_{L0} . After adding some loss in form of a series resistance Z_{rser} , we get the result in fig. 4.

Nonlinear versions of components can also be created. If the inductor were to saturate, its relative inductance would

Fig. 4: The 1st order kernel of a Volterra inductor with series resistance $Z_{L0} + Z_{rser}$; $L = 100 \text{ nH}$, $R_{ser} = 3 \Omega$, with $dt = 1 \text{ ns}$, $N = 300$

Fig. 5: Frequency response of the Volterra inductor. In a wide midband, phase angle approaches $\frac{\pi}{2} \approx 1.57$. The phase transition is smooth at the Nyquist frequency

be a function of the current i , and could be expressed by a Taylor series $T_N(i)$ with coefficients $a_0\dots a_P$, in total giving the momentary inductance $T_N(i)L_0$. We integrate this series once, and sort the resulting coefficients into the corresponding Volterra series N 's kernels at $\tau_1\dots\tau_p = 0$:

$$n_1(0) = 1 \cdot a_0 \quad (32)$$

$$n_2(0,0) = 1/2 \cdot a_1$$

$$n_3(0,0,0) = 1/3 \cdot a_2$$

...

We can show this by integrating the voltage across the inductor up to time t :

$$\int_0^t u(\tau) d\tau = \int_0^t T_N(i)L_0 \frac{di}{d\tau} d\tau \quad , \quad (33)$$

We can now bring this back into the time-derivative form:

$$u(t) = L_0 \frac{d}{dt} \int_0^{i(t)} T_N(i) di \quad , \quad (34)$$

which contains L_0 times the derivative operator $\frac{d}{dt}$ (which we already modeled by the linear, discrete-time inductor) composed with (acting on) the Taylor series, integrated over the current.

Now, we get the total impedance $Z_{total} = Z_{L0}N + Z_{rser}$, which can easily be calculated using the composition (see section II-B) and addition operators.

Other nonlinear, dynamic components can be created similarly.

G. A Short Example

Here, we give a short example on how to calculate a circuit model using the previously described techniques, and compare the resulting behaviour to a SPICE simulation.

We take the system shown in fig. 6a as reference. It contains a lossy nonlinear inductor (saturating at 1 A), a lossy

Fig. 6: Oscillatory system with two nonlinear components L and D : (a) Circuit schematic, R_{ser} and G_{par} symbolize L/C component losses; (b) Test input, (c) Response of the Large-Signal (LS) and Small-Signal (SS) systems in SPICE and Volterra.

linear capacitor, and a diode to form a nonlinearly dampened resonant circuit. The diode is chosen to have a very soft I-V characteristic, reminiscent of detector diodes, and is modeled as a 5th order approximation of the shockley equation. The components have the following specifications:

- Inductor: $L_0 = 5 \text{ nH}$; $L(i) = L_0 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{i^2}{1 \text{ A}^2}\right)$; $R_{ser} = 0.05 \Omega$
- Capacitor: $C = 200 \text{ pF}$, $G_{par} = 3.3 \text{ mS}$
- Diode: $i(u) = \frac{1}{50} \frac{\text{A}}{\text{V}} \cdot \sum_{p=1}^5 \frac{u^p}{p! V^{p-1}}$

The Volterra transfer operator of the RLC system now becomes:

$$G = Z_D || Z_C (Z_L + Z_D || Z_C)^{\leftarrow 1}, \quad (35)$$

which is very simple compared to other notations of similar problems [13], limiting the need for manual calculations. It closely resembles the equation for a linear circuit's transfer function; there, we would be able to cancel terms in denominator and numerator.

In our algebra, it is structurally the same: When we have a forward operator followed by an inverse, in both of them we can cancel terms from the right (see eq. 15), so the expression further simplifies:

$$G = \left(J + Z_L (Z_D || Z_C)^{\leftarrow 1} \right)^{\leftarrow 1}, \quad (36)$$

which also is computationally more efficient; not only because of the reduction of terms, but also because some inversions

will cancel if the parallel operator is written out.

Our example model has a base timestep of 1 ns . In figures 6b and 6c we plot the resulting system's response against a SPICE simulation - both for the large-signal case (blue), and for a small-signal case (orange), in which all models are linearized. We use 5-fold Volterra Kernel Interpolation [14] to account for up to 5th order harmonics, overall resulting in a 200 ps render timestep. The SPICE response is also resampled to 200 ps .

Observing the responses, we can identify nonlinear effects in both SPICE and Volterra implementations by comparing the blue against the orange curves. A large signal increases resonant frequency and decreases resonance quality compared to a small signal.

Then, comparing the Volterra simulations to their corresponding SPICE simulations, we see that while slight deviations are visible, the curves track closely. Deviations can be attributed to truncation errors, and differences between the SPICE and Volterra models due to smoothing around Ω_N .

Using Volterra Kernel Interpolation, we can calculate out-of-band harmonics at the cost of only a simple *sinc* convolution - the number of kernel entries does not have to be increased. This is especially useful for nonlinear systems which resemble the 'Wiener' type, where the harmonic-generating nonlinearity comes last, but will also increase accuracy for 'Hammerstein' or mixed types. The placement of nonlinear elements in a transfer equation (like eq. 35, for example) can give hints to where the nonlinearity is generated, and whether out-of-band harmonics would be filtered out by low-pass behaviour.

In general, such simplifications as used in eq. 36 can result in a very significant speedup of calculations. Inversions are the most computationally intensive calculations, followed by compositions and then additions/subtractions. For the case of two stacked voltage dividers, for example, a straightforward transfer calculation would need 8 inversions, 3 compositions, and 6 additions. By simplifying, we can get to 2 inversions, 3 compositions, 4 additions.

The concept of maximum incremental gain [George Zames] might also be worth mentioning at this point: If a sum of operators contains one with dominant gain, the others might be neglected with little error; leading to further simplifications.

III. TWO-PORT SYSTEMS

A. A Recap of the Linear Case

Now that nonlinear one-port impedances have been described, we can shift our attention to two-port systems, which allow for a more advanced circuit analysis. In [11], some of the operations (addition, composition, feedback) reported here are defined for frequency domain.

Fig. 7: The system \mathcal{H} with port 1 (left) and port 2 (right)

When calculating with two-port systems, we always deal with two-component signals. Those can be, for example, voltage u and current i (as in ABCD parameters), but other representations (like incident and reflected waves a and b for S-parameters) are also possible. We will stay in ABCD form for now; other representations will be discussed in section IV.

For a simplified notation, we can introduce a signal vector \vec{r} , which is a combination of both voltage and current time series:

$$\vec{r}(n) = \begin{pmatrix} u(n) \\ i(n) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (37)$$

A nonlinear two-port has two ports. They exhibit voltages and currents $\vec{r}_1 = (u_1 \ i_1)^T$ and $\vec{r}_2 = (u_2 \ i_2)^T$; thus two input variables control two output variables, and we have a MIMO system.

In linear circuit theory, they are linked by ABCD parameters. Since we restrict ourselves to time domain, the corresponding operator needs to be a convolution $*$,

$$\vec{r}_2(n) = \begin{pmatrix} a * u_1(n) + b * i_1(n) \\ c * u_1(n) + d * i_1(n) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (38)$$

applying the FIR filter representation a, b, c, d of our ABCD-parameters to the input signal \vec{r}_1 comprised of u_1, i_1 .

B. The Nonlinear Case

For proposing a nonlinear equivalent, we can make use of MIMO Volterra systems. Such systems have first been discussed in [2], [19], but to our knowledge not thoroughly embedded into a wider circuit theory context. Fig. 7 shows the nonlinear system \mathcal{H} , containing a set of two-input volterra operators \mathbb{H}_u and \mathbb{H}_i - each taking in a full signal $(u \ i)^T$, but only yielding either a voltage or a current:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} u_2(n) \\ i_2(n) \end{pmatrix} &= \vec{r}_2(n) = \mathcal{H} \vec{r}_1(n) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{H}_u \\ \mathbb{H}_i \end{pmatrix} \vec{r}_1(n) \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{H}_u \\ \mathbb{H}_i \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u_1(n) \\ i_1(n) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{H}_u \begin{pmatrix} u_1(n) \\ i_1(n) \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbb{H}_i \begin{pmatrix} u_1(n) \\ i_1(n) \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

so that

$$u_2(n) = \mathbb{H}_u \vec{r}_1(n) \quad ; \quad i_2(n) = \mathbb{H}_i \vec{r}_1(n) \quad . \quad (39)$$

\mathbb{H}_u is the signal-to-voltage conversion series, and incorporates, as we will later see, the convolution with parameters a and b ; \mathbb{H}_i is the signal-to-current conversion series, incorporating the convolution with parameters c and d .

The set of those two MISO systems \mathbb{H}_u and \mathbb{H}_i fully describes a nonlinear two-port system \mathcal{H} (see eq. 39). It converts a voltage and a current into another one of each (a 2I2O system).

A closer look at the system \mathcal{H} and its two subsystems $\mathbb{H}_{u/i}$ gives an insight into how nonlinear effects are captured. In general, a two-input conversion series up to order P is given as

$$\mathbb{H}_u \vec{r}_1 = \sum_{p=0}^P \mathbb{H}_{u,p} \vec{r}_1 \quad (40)$$

in which the p -th order part is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{H}_{u,p} \vec{r}_1 &= \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^p \sum_{\tau_1 \dots \tau_i=0}^{T_p} \sum_{v_1 \dots v_j=0}^{T_p} h_{u,p;i,j}((\tau_1 \dots \tau_i), (v_1 \dots v_j)) \\ &\quad \times \prod_{l=0}^i u_1(n - \tau_l) \prod_{m=0}^j i_1(n - v_m) \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

with $j = p - i$. The kernel $h_{u,p;i,j}$ is the p -th order kernel with i voltage inputs and j current inputs (which are just the length of the set of τ and v respectively, and are thus often omitted for clarity).

By examining this equation, we can see that in the linear case of ($p = 1, i = 1, j = 0$) the series simply collapses to the convolution with a in equation 38; in the case of ($p = 1, i = 0, j = 1$), it is the convolution with b . The same holds for $\mathbb{H}_{i,p}$ and c, d ; and in effect, all convolutions with the $abcd$ matrix are contained. Furthermore, this approach contains all higher-order monomials, that can be generated from time-shifted u and i .

For the linear case, this operation is very clear: The system \mathcal{H} fully contains the ABCD matrix. One might then wonder: Now, why do we need this system \mathcal{H} at all? Why not just transform it into 4 distinct one-input Volterra Series $A u(n), B i(n), C u(n), D i(n)$, which are used as drop-in replacement for the convolution in equation 38, thus staying closer to the original notation?

The simple answer is: This can be helpful under certain circumstances, as we will explore later; but in general, this loses information, and is therefore only a projection instead of a transformation.

One intuitive hint at this can already be seen by computing the number of kernels, needed to describe the system. The p th order 2-input subsystem $\mathbb{H}_{u/i,p}$ not only contains the information of a voltage signal and a current signal to the p -th

power each (u^p or i^p), but also information on mixed-order voltage and current products ($u^i \cdot p^j$ with $i + j = p$). In general, the p -th order two-input kernel therefore contains $p + 1$ times the information of a regular one-input volterra kernel. Thus, only for $p \leq 1$, system information would always be preserved - here we have two 1st-order two-input kernels, giving $2 \cdot (p + 1) = 4$ times the information of a single kernel, corresponding to our four parameters a, b, c, d . But if the order is increased ($p > 1$), this is not necessarily true, since mixed-order voltage/current kernels might be present.

Reflecting on all of this, it can be said that the new operator \mathcal{H} relates input and output in the same way as an ABCD matrix does (Let's say it has ABCD form, to make this relationship clear). Additionally, it captures nonlinear behaviour. However, it can not, without loss, be separated into four individual SISO Volterra components A,B,C,D.

C. Two-Input Volterra Series, Operations on Operators

Now that the systems are defined, we can begin to see how they might be useful. One may want to **chain** two systems \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{K} , in which case the mathematical operation simply is written

$$\vec{r}_2(n) = (\mathcal{K} \circ \mathcal{G}) \vec{r}_1(n) = \mathcal{K}\mathcal{G} \vec{r}_1(n) = \mathcal{H} \vec{r}_1(n) \quad (42)$$

They form the composite system \mathcal{H} , for which a formula and more general information is given in subsection III-D. The newly defined nonlinear system shares an important property with ABCD parameters: It is easily chainable.

Systems can also be **added** or **subtracted**. The addition of two systems is given by:

$$\vec{r}_2(n) = (\mathcal{K} + \mathcal{G})\vec{r}_1(n) = \mathcal{K}\vec{r}_1(n) + \mathcal{G}\vec{r}_1(n) = \mathcal{H}\vec{r}_1(n) \quad , \quad (43)$$

and subtractions are performed in a similar way. Both operations are done by applying the +/- operator element-wise on both kernels.

D. Details on System Composition

For **composing** two two-port systems, we have extended Kielkiewicz' solution [8] towards the zeroth order, and two-input series:

$$\begin{aligned} h_{up;i,j}((\tau_1 \dots \tau_i), (v_1 \dots v_j)) = & \\ & \sum_{x=0}^P \sum_{l=0}^x \sum_{\substack{\forall abcd: \\ \Sigma a + \Sigma c = i \\ \Sigma b + \Sigma d = j}} k_{u;x;l,m}((s_1 \dots s_l), (\sigma_1 \dots \sigma_m)) \\ & \times g_{u;a_1,b_1}((\tau_1 - s_1, \dots, \tau_{a_1} - s_1), (v_1 - \sigma_1, \dots, v_{b_1} - \sigma_1)) \times \dots \\ & \times g_{u;a_l,b_l}((\tau_{\gamma_a} - s_l, \dots, \tau_{\Sigma a} - s_l), (v_{\gamma_b} - \sigma_l, \dots, v_{\Sigma b} - \sigma_l)) \\ & \times g_{i;c_1,d_1}((\tau_1 - s_1, \dots, \tau_{c_1} - s_1), (v_1 - \sigma_1, \dots, v_{d_1} - \sigma_1)) \times \dots \\ & \times g_{i;c_m,d_m}((\tau_{\gamma_c} - s_m, \dots, \tau_{\Sigma c} - s_m), (v_{\gamma_d} - \sigma_m, \dots, v_{\Sigma d} - \sigma_m)) \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

with $m = x - l$, $\gamma_a = \Sigma a - a_l + 1, \dots, \gamma_d = \Sigma d - d_m + 1$.

TODO: This seems to contain an error in the indices of s, σ .

This might look simple¹, but actually will take considerable effort to calculate.

E. Inversion of nonlinear two-port systems

Furthermore, systems need to be **inverted** for many applications. For inverse systems $\mathcal{I} = \mathcal{H}^{-1}$, the following relationship holds:

$$\mathcal{H}\mathcal{I} \vec{r}(n) = \vec{r}(n) \quad (45)$$

Carini, Sicuranza and Mathews in [1] have given a recursive procedure, which we simply adapt to MIMO systems:

$$\mathcal{I}_p \vec{r}(n) = \mathcal{I}_1 \vec{r}(n) - \mathcal{I}_1 [\mathcal{H}'_p \mathcal{I}_{p-1} \vec{r}(n)] \quad , \quad (46)$$

$$\text{with } \mathcal{I}_1 \vec{r}(n) = \mathcal{H}_1^{-1} \vec{r}(n) \quad , \quad (47)$$

$$\text{and } \mathcal{H}'_p \vec{r}(n) = \mathcal{H}_2 \vec{r}(n) + \dots + \mathcal{H}_p \vec{r}(n) \quad . \quad (48)$$

The system \mathcal{H}_1^{-1} is mathematically equivalent to the inverse ABCD matrix of the linear part of the circuit. This procedure applies to signals, instead of systems. But noting that all required operations (namely, 1st order inversion, addition, subtraction and composition) have already been introduced in the previous subsection also on an operator level, nothing prevents us from directly and efficiently calculating the inverse to a given system (without applying it to any signal). For this, every occurrence of the $\vec{r}(n)$ can simply be skipped in the above formulae, and operations are directly performed on the MIMO operators, yielding an inverse system with much greater computational efficiency than from Schetzen's original formula.

¹If the dots ... are not left out, we get 3139 unique g-kernel terms for a fifth-order system.

IV. TRANSFORMATIONS BETWEEN PARAMETER TYPES

When working with two-port systems, one or another representation is often more useful for specific cases; hence we need to transformed between parameter types.

While we can often generalize from linear to nonlinear theory, the usual linear conversion equations [cite here] fundamentally can not include mixed-order terms (and each system is more than just 4 Volterra series, as discussed in section III-B), so another approach is needed. In [17], for example, Verbeyst makes use of a transformation procedure between nonlinear S- and T-parameters in order to calculate the behaviour of cascaded systems. The procedure is iterative, and based on numerically generating the cascaded system's output, and then characterising it.

A general procedure has not been demonstrated, however; and the method given by Verbeyst is costly. Therefore, we introduce an operator-based approach, which has the additional advantage of being very simple to implement, and yielding all other important transformations just as easily.

A. General Procedure for Transformations

Here, we want to derive some auxiliary operators, which later allow to transform between different parameter types. Namely, these are field/wave transformation operators (IV-A1), and swap operators (IV-A2). We have decided to denote those operators \bar{O} with a bar; they are of the same structure as normal MIMO operators, but a special sign makes their purpose more clear and prevents them from being confused with same-letter systems.

1) *Field/Wave Transformation*: When using the usual parameter types, we distinguish between two signal types: *voltage & current* signals (field quantities), used with ABCD, Y, G, H, Z parameters, or *incident & reflected* signals (wave quantities), used with S, T parameters.

For getting the **field signal from the the wave signal**, we introduce $\bar{\mathcal{F}}$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} u \\ i \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{Z_0} & \sqrt{Z_0} \\ 1/\sqrt{Z_0} & -1/\sqrt{Z_0} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a \\ b \end{pmatrix} = \bar{\mathcal{F}} \begin{pmatrix} a \\ b \end{pmatrix} \quad (49)$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{f}_{u,1}((0), ()) &= \sqrt{Z_0} ; & \bar{f}_{u,1}((), (0)) &= \sqrt{Z_0} ; \\ \bar{f}_{i,1}((0), ()) &= 1/\sqrt{Z_0} ; & \bar{f}_{i,1}((), (0)) &= -1/\sqrt{Z_0} . \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

For getting the **wave signal from a field signal**, we introduce $\bar{\mathcal{W}}$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a \\ b \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/2\sqrt{Z_0} & \sqrt{Z_0}/2 \\ 1/2\sqrt{Z_0} & -\sqrt{Z_0}/2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ i \end{pmatrix} = \bar{\mathcal{W}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ i \end{pmatrix} \quad (51)$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}_{a,1}((0), ()) &= 1/2\sqrt{Z_0} ; & \bar{w}_{a,1}((), (0)) &= \sqrt{Z_0}/2 ; \\ \bar{w}_{b,1}((0), ()) &= 1/2\sqrt{Z_0} ; & \bar{w}_{b,1}((), (0)) &= -\sqrt{Z_0}/2 . \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

$\bar{\mathcal{F}}$ and $\bar{\mathcal{W}}$ are inverses of each other.

2) *Signal Swap Transformations*: Then, looking at the parameters, we see that they often feature wave or field signals of the same type, but in different ordering. For example, ABCD parameters give the relation

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ i_1 \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{H} \begin{pmatrix} u_2 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix} , \quad (53)$$

while Z parameters give

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{Z} \begin{pmatrix} i_1 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix} . \quad (54)$$

We can see, that in this example, the positions of i_1 and u_2 have swapped across the diagonal while changing the parameter type. Therefore, we need a cross-side swap operation to transform from ABCD to Z parameters. It will be defined later.

If we now also want to include G parameters, we furthermore need the same-side swap operator $\bar{\mathcal{S}}$. Again beginning with ABCD parameters, first swapping u_1 and i_1 , and then doing the cross-side swap of u_1, u_2 afterwards, we would arrive at:

$$\begin{pmatrix} i_1 \\ u_2 \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{G} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix} . \quad (55)$$

Together with the field/wave transformations, those two kinds of operations are all that is needed for transforming between all commonly used parameter types. Therefore, in the following, we want to give those two operations in a very general way, for an arbitrary system \mathcal{X} with arbitrary quantities x (serving as placeholder for any of the parameter or signal types). Let us define this system first:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{X} \begin{pmatrix} x_3 \\ x_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{X}_1 \\ \mathbb{X}_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_3 \\ x_4 \end{pmatrix} . \quad (56)$$

For its inverse, we can write:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_3 \\ x_4 \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{X}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{X}_3^{-1} \\ \mathbb{X}_4^{-1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} , \quad (57)$$

The **cross-side swap operation** is a little involved and does not have a fixed operator; it has two, and they have to be recalculated every time they are used.

If we want to derive the (arbitrary) parameter set \mathcal{Y} from \mathcal{X} , for which holds

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{Y} \begin{pmatrix} x_2 \\ x_4 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (58)$$

(using the same signals from eq. 56) we can introduce the systems $\bar{\mathcal{E}}$, $\bar{\mathcal{D}}$ and write:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix} = \bar{\mathcal{E}} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{Y} \bar{\mathcal{D}} \begin{pmatrix} x_3 \\ x_4 \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{Y} \begin{pmatrix} x_2 \\ x_4 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (59)$$

$\bar{\mathcal{E}}$ gets x_1, x_3 from x_1, x_2 ; $\bar{\mathcal{D}}$ gets x_2, x_4 from x_3, x_4 . From this, we see that

$$\mathcal{X} = \bar{\mathcal{E}}^{-1} \mathcal{Y} \bar{\mathcal{D}}, \quad (60)$$

which, using the basic algebra for nonlinear systems, leads to the final result:

$$\mathcal{Y} = \bar{\mathcal{E}} \mathcal{X} \bar{\mathcal{D}}^{-1}. \quad (61)$$

The operator $\bar{\mathcal{E}}$ is given by:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix} = \bar{\mathcal{E}} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\mathbb{E}}_1 \\ \bar{\mathbb{X}}_3^{-1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ \bar{\mathbb{X}}_3^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} \quad (62)$$

where $\bar{e}_{1,1}((0), (0)) = 1$. We get $\bar{\mathbb{X}}_3^{-1}$ from eq. 57.

The operator $\bar{\mathcal{D}}$ is given by:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_2 \\ x_4 \end{pmatrix} = \bar{\mathcal{D}} \begin{pmatrix} x_3 \\ x_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\mathbb{X}}_2 \\ \bar{\mathbb{D}}_4 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_3 \\ x_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\mathbb{X}}_2 \begin{pmatrix} x_3 \\ x_4 \end{pmatrix} \\ x_4 \end{pmatrix} \quad (63)$$

where $\bar{d}_{4,1}((0), (0)) = 1$, and $\bar{\mathbb{X}}_2$ is taken from eq. 56.

Note that both operators refer to the operator which they enclose (whose signals are to be swapped, in this case \mathcal{X}), forming a parametrized sandwich operator - they are not fixed, but have to be individually recalculated for each operator they are used on.

The **same-side swap operation** $\bar{\mathcal{S}}$ is simply given by

$$\bar{s}_{1,1}((0), (0)) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{s}_{2,1}((0), (0)) = 1, \quad (64)$$

which results in

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} = \bar{\mathcal{S}} \begin{pmatrix} x_2 \\ x_1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (65)$$

$\bar{\mathcal{S}}$ is the inverse of itself.

Fig. 8: The available transformations

B. A Few Useful Transformations

From these operators, the transformation rules between all types of parameters can now be established. We have done that for the following cases:

$$\underline{\text{ABDC}} \rightarrow \underline{\text{Z}}: \quad \mathcal{Z} = \bar{\mathcal{E}} \mathcal{A} \bar{\mathcal{D}}^{-1}$$

$$\underline{\text{Z}} \rightarrow \underline{\text{ABCD}}: \quad \mathcal{A} = \bar{\mathcal{E}} \mathcal{Z} \bar{\mathcal{D}}^{-1}$$

$$\underline{\text{Z}} \rightarrow \underline{\text{Y}}: \quad \mathcal{Y} = \mathcal{Z}^{-1} \quad (\text{and vice versa})$$

$$\underline{\text{ABCD}} \rightarrow \underline{\text{G}}: \quad \mathcal{G} = \bar{\mathcal{E}} (\bar{\mathcal{S}} \mathcal{A}) \bar{\mathcal{D}}^{-1}$$

$$\underline{\text{G}} \rightarrow \underline{\text{ABCD}}: \quad \mathcal{A} = \bar{\mathcal{S}} \bar{\mathcal{E}} \mathcal{G} \bar{\mathcal{D}}^{-1}$$

$$\underline{\text{G}} \rightarrow \underline{\text{H}}: \quad \mathcal{H} = \mathcal{G}^{-1} \quad (\text{and vice versa})$$

$$\underline{\text{ABCD}} \rightarrow \underline{\text{T}}: \quad \mathcal{T} = \bar{\mathcal{S}} \bar{\mathcal{W}} \mathcal{A} \bar{\mathcal{F}}$$

$$\underline{\text{T}} \rightarrow \underline{\text{ABCD}}: \quad \mathcal{A} = \bar{\mathcal{F}} \bar{\mathcal{S}} \mathcal{T} \bar{\mathcal{W}}$$

$$\underline{\text{T}} \rightarrow \underline{\text{S}}: \quad \mathcal{S} = \bar{\mathcal{E}} (\mathcal{T} \bar{\mathcal{S}}) \bar{\mathcal{D}}^{-1}$$

$$\underline{\text{S}} \rightarrow \underline{\text{T}}: \quad \mathcal{T} = \bar{\mathcal{E}} \mathcal{S} \bar{\mathcal{D}}^{-1} \bar{\mathcal{S}}$$

This is not an all-to-all mapping - but the missing transformations can easily be derived, or construed by chaining two transformation steps. In some cases, the systems are not invertible.

C. Combinations of Networks

TODO: Brune's test, parallel and series connections

1) *Two-port and two-port*: Since composed systems were already discussed in III-D, we now want to go to other connections of systems; namely, we will give the example of a series connection of two nonlinear two-port systems. For that, we bring both of our systems into Z-parameter form, and get $\mathcal{Z}_1, \mathcal{Z}_2$. Our overall series system is now

$$\mathcal{Z} = \mathcal{Z}_1 + \mathcal{Z}_2 \quad (66)$$

Further types of system connections can also be analyzed, like series-parallel (\mathcal{H}), parallel-series (\mathcal{G}), or pure parallel (\mathcal{Y}), reflecting the parameter types given by [5]. In each case, we transform to the correct parameter types first, then perform simple kernel additions similar to our example, and

Fig. 9: The shunt impedance Z is described as a two-port with an open output connection, allowing us to compose both systems into one: $\mathcal{B} = \mathcal{A}\mathcal{Z}$

then transform back if needed.

2) *Two-port and one-port:* When a one-port network (Here: an impedance Z) is connected to a two-port network \mathcal{A} (in ABCD form), the two-port's input will present an impedance Z_{in} . It can be calculated in the following way.

First, the impedance Z is transformed into a two-port shunt impedance \mathcal{Z} using the same procedure that later is defined in eqs. 73 and 74.

Then, we compose this system \mathcal{Z} with system \mathcal{A} (see fig. 9) to form system \mathcal{B} :

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ i_1 \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{B} \begin{pmatrix} u_3 \\ i_3 \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{A}\mathcal{Z} \begin{pmatrix} u_3 \\ i_3 \end{pmatrix} . \quad (67)$$

When the resulting system's right-hand port is open, its current will be zero, and thus all terms containing at least one current input collapse to zero. This greatly simplifies things, as it allows us to reduce the 2I2O system to two SISO systems B'_u and B'_i , which give us voltage and current of the left port. Their kernels can be obtained by the following reduction:

$$b'_{up}(\tau_1 \dots \tau_p) = b_{up;p,0}((\tau_1 \dots \tau_p), ()) , \quad (68)$$

and

$$b'_{ip}(v_1 \dots v_p) = b_{ip;0,p}((v_1 \dots v_p)) . \quad (69)$$

Now, the input impedance (relating voltage to current) is:

$$Z_{in} = B'_u(B'_i)^{-1} \quad (70)$$

V. IDENTIFICATION OF SYSTEMS

In this section, a few ways to identify or calculate a system from schematics, or from black-box measurements, are given.

A. Determination from schematics

If a schematic of Volterra impedances is given, the ABCD-parameter representation of the total circuit can be calculated using the method we present here. First, the schematic is broken up into elementary systems, which each contain only one shunt- or series pass element, see figs. 10 and 11.

Those building blocks already allow us to recreate our schematic as a series of two-port systems. This applies to any two-port networks with lumped elements, like Pi-networks, filters, voltage dividers, et cetera.

Fig. 10: Series network

Fig. 11: Shunt network

Now, starting from one side of the chain of systems, we compose the system with the next one, until all are composed together, yielding the overall parameter set of the system.

For that, we need, of course, a description of the individual systems. It is easy to see that the series system in fig. 10 performs the following operation:

$$\mathcal{H}_{ser} \vec{r}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} u_1 - Z i_1 \\ i_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (71)$$

From this, the two-input kernels $h_u((\tau_1 \dots), (v_1 \dots))$, $h_i((\tau_1 \dots), (v_1 \dots))$ of \mathcal{H}_{ser} 's subsystems \mathbb{H}_u , \mathbb{H}_i can be constructed using the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{H}_u = u_1 - Z i_1 &\Rightarrow h_{u,1}((0), ()) = 1 ; & (72) \\ h_{u,1}((v_1)) &= -z_1(v_1) ; \\ h_{u,2}((v_1, v_2)) &= -z_2(v_1, v_2) ; \\ &\dots \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{and } \mathbb{H}_i = i_1 \Rightarrow h_{i,1}((v_1)) = 1 .$$

The shunt system in fig. 11 can similarly be constructed using the following equations, with $Y = Z^{-1}$ being the admittance of Z :

$$\mathcal{H}_{sh} \vec{r}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ i_1 - Y u_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (73)$$

Now, the two-input kernels of its subsystems \mathbb{H}_u , \mathbb{H}_i are:

$$\mathbb{H}_u \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ i_1 \end{pmatrix} = u_1 \Rightarrow h_{u,1}((0), ()) = 1 , \quad (74)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \mathbb{H}_i \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ i_1 \end{pmatrix} &= i_1 - Y u_1 \Rightarrow h_{i,1}((v_1)) = 1 ; \\ h_{i,1}((\tau_1)) &= -y_1(\tau_1) ; \\ h_{i,2}((\tau_1, \tau_2)) &= -y_2(\tau_1, \tau_2) ; \\ &\dots \end{aligned}$$

With all kernels of all subsystems now being known, they can be composed using the technique in III-D. Section II-E might help with simplifying networks by collapsing a series or parallel connection of impedances into a single impedance.

B. Black-Box characterization

The system ports are connected to two uncorrelated noise sources with internal impedance Z_0 . A nonlinear 2-port \mathcal{H} can be identified using the following procedure: First, a suitable input into the system needs to be defined. In our case, the characterization procedure is derived from the Lee-Schetzen method; Here, one important requirement for the input signal is a low level of correlation between input samples. In a system in \mathcal{H} form,

$$\begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ i_1 \end{pmatrix} = \mathcal{H} \begin{pmatrix} u_2 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (75)$$

this is not fulfilled: u_2 will most likely correlate with i_2 , since the impedance Z_0 presented by the noise source - connected at port 2 - couples current and voltage. Therefore, we propose a two-step solution. First, the norton equivalent voltages of the noise sources are calculated:

$$u_n = u + Z_0 \cdot i \quad (76)$$

TODO: Since the current arrows are defined in opposing directions in figure 7, $u_{n2} = u_2 - Z_0 \cdot i_2$. This needs to be updated in the following formulae

Then, we take those norton voltages as the inputs into the system, and the currents as the output of the system, forming the **Norton-referred system** λ :

$$\begin{pmatrix} i_1 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix} = \lambda \begin{pmatrix} u_{n1} \\ u_{n2} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (77)$$

This now has the advantage that both inputs u_{n1} and u_{n2} are uncorrelated, and can easily be obtained from measured data. This system is therefore the first step to obtain \mathcal{H} . By introducing the **Norton transformation system** \mathcal{N} that transforms between voltages and norton voltages

$$\begin{pmatrix} i_1 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix} = \lambda \left(\mathcal{N} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{pmatrix} \right) = \lambda \begin{pmatrix} u_{n1} \\ u_{n2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (78)$$

we can, after a few steps, calculate the admittance system \mathcal{Y} , which (by a step given in the following section) can then finally be transformed to H :

$$\mathcal{Y} = \lambda \circ \mathcal{N} = \lambda \circ (\mathcal{J} - Z_0 \cdot \lambda)^{-1}, \quad (79)$$

where \mathcal{J} is the identity system, which transforms a signal or a system into itself.

Fig. 12: Closed-loop system with forward path A and feedback path F .

VI. FEEDBACK IN NONLINEAR SYSTEMS

The general method for determining the Volterra operators of feedback systems is given in this section. We start with SISO systems, as the procedure reminds of the well-known linear case; then some considerations on designing control loops is given, and later we apply the same theory to two-port (MIMO) systems.

A. SISO systems

We begin by representing the closed-loop system H by a forward Volterra operator A and a feedback Volterra operator F (see fig.12).

Since we have

$$x(n) = \bar{x}(n) + FA\bar{x}(n) = (J + FA)\bar{x}(n), \quad (80)$$

the total closed-loop operator H , which lets $y(n) = Hx(n)$, can now easily be calculated to be

$$H = A(J + FA)^{-1}, \quad (81)$$

where J is the identity system, transforming a signal or a system into itself. This equation has been given [10], but in the following section, we want to expand on it a little.

B. Consequences of Consequences

It is not immediately obvious why equation 81 is able to model the complex effects that might be introduced by feedback in nonlinear systems. As it displays no obvious recursion in time, it would be conceivable that it cannot explain *causal chains*: phenomena that only emerge due to multiple cycles of the system interacting with itself. However, this intuition would be wrong; and the equation can indeed model such effects, which we want to show with an example. Consider systems A and F with

$$a_1[0] = 0.33, \quad f_1[1] = -1.$$

A single impulse of amplitude 1 is now applied at the input. The output will show quick exponential decay with base 0.33. Now, let's include a new term: $a_2[4, 9] = 3$, creating system $A1$: This kernel, on its own, will not contribute significantly with the given input, which can be seen in fig 13.

Instead of this nonlinear term, let's now include $a_2[5, 5] = 0.33$, creating the system $A2$. A second pulse appears at the

Fig. 13: Partial test system A1 inside a feedback loop, with nonlinear component $a_2(4, 9) = 3$. The output pulses die down quickly.

Fig. 14: Partial test system A2 inside a feedback loop, with nonlinear component $a_2(5, 5) = 0.333$. The output pulses die down quickly.

Fig. 15: The full test system A inside a feedback loop, with both components $a_2(4, 9) = 3$ and $a_2(5, 5) = 0.333$. Repeating pulses occur due to the interaction of both nonlinear terms: We get more than the sum of the parts.

output, but after that, the pulses die down quickly (see fig. 14), and the nonlinear term on its own cannot produce a sustained pulse train.

When we combine both nonlinear terms however, we suddenly see a new feature: Sustained pulses can occur, which is a new quality to our simple nonlinear system. Observing figure 15, we can draw two conclusions:

- The system behaviour is more complex than the sum of its parts - we see emergent behaviour, due to causal chains.
- Increasingly higher orders encode for the increasingly longer overall impulse response, i.e. for the pulses further down on the time axis. On large time scales, the system will react strongly to the initial conditions; this feature can be very prominent in nonlinear systems with feedback, and might even lead to chaos.

This illustrates that equation 81 is indeed capable of modeling complex causal chains without having to simulate them explicitly in time domain - it does not rely recursively on previous timesteps. We suspect that the emergent phenom-

TABLE II: Test System Parameters

System	Equation
System A ('Forward')	$y[n] = x[n] + x^3[n]$
System F ('Feedback')	$y[n] = 0.7x[n - 1]$

ena still can appear due to eq. 8 being *recursive in order*, replacing the need of being *recursive in time*, as numerical integration methods are. While the domain of recursion might differ, higher orders still generally correspond to longer-term responses - a striking similarity, but no perfect equivalence.

Note that in our example, the maximum order is limited to 5, and maximum kernel length is limited to 20. Due to these limitations, longer pulse trains cannot be modeled, since both higher orders and higher kernel lengths would be needed. Still, the example serves to demonstrate the phenomena appearing in nonlinear systems with feedback.

The stability of nonlinear feedback systems is determined not only by the small-signal stability (frequency-domain zeros of $1 + FA$ have negative real parts), but also by the convergence volume of $(J + FA)^{-1}$. This T -dimensional volume extends around the operating point (with T being the memory length of the Volterra operator) and contains the set of all possible input samples $x(n - T) \dots x(n)$ that will result in a stable system output - reflecting the fact that some nonlinear systems can be stable for small inputs, but become unstable once a large enough input has been reached. In the context of nonlinear systems, stability can be defined as having a finite-length system response.

Stability is very hard to determine analytically. When the input signal brings a system to the edge of instability, the system will react strongly to even miniscule differences in the input waveform. This effect can only be captured by kernels of very high orders, which, as a consequence, will mainly be responsible for modelling the edge-of-instability behaviour, and by definition this also corresponds to very high kernel lengths. This is particularly hard to compute.

Figures ?? and ?? show the responses of an example feedback system towards stimuli of different amplitudes. We can see that this is mainly due to the third-order response extending longer than the first order, and the fifth order even more so, although starting slowly. This demonstrates that higher-order effects play a comparatively big role right at the edge of instability, where only a small increase in input amplitude can cause the impulse response to suddenly become much longer - which is in line with the intuition that such a sudden reaction towards the input should only be possible due to a nonlinear function rising very steeply at its edges, requiring a polynomial relation of very high order.

In practice, we recommend applying a test signal resembling the use case, for example a white gaussian noise $x(n) \sim N(\mu_x, \sigma_x^2)$, to the input of $y(n) = (J + FA)^{-1} x(n)$,

Fig. 16: 1st + 2nd order test system response to a single 1 V impulse. Each order is marked in a different colour; even orders are zero, because the system is symmetrical. The overall system response is shown in black, and is dominated by first-order (linear) behaviour.

Fig. 17: 1st + 4th order test system response to a single 1 V impulse.

and then calculating $z(n) = (J + FA)y(n)$. If the difference between z and x grows too large at a given σ_x^2 , the Volterra system would probably be close to diverging at this noise variance (however, it might also mean that truncation errors already play a role). In the real world, this would show up as sustained oscillations, subharmonic locking to the input signal, or chaotic behaviour. As Volterra series can inherently only show finite-length responses, a sustained instability like an oscillation or chaos can not be modelled by them, but will be hinted at by diverging behaviour.

For MIMO systems, this becomes a little bit more complicated.

C. Control Loop Design

The general structure of a control system is shown in figure 18.

Nonlinear control tasks can easily be tackled using Volterra operators, starting from standard linear procedures. Here, we have the choice to either keep it simple, choosing just a desired closed-loop transfer operator G , or, additionally, the disturbance transfer operator G_s . In both cases, we need a compute unit that implements the controller R ; in the second case, we additionally need the freedom to choose a transfer operator for the sensor S , which might require another compute unit.

Fig. 18: Controller R , plant H and sensor S form a closed control loop. The signal $d(n)$ disturbs the output.

The procedure for determining a suitable nonlinear controller now begins by following the usual principles at first:

- Linearize components around the design operating point
- Use any standard LTI procedure for designing the control loop around this operating point (root locus, pole placement, frequency-domain loop shaping, etc.)
- Using this design, calculate the resulting closed-loop transfer function $G(s)$
- (Optionally): Calculate the resulting disturbance transfer function $G_s(s)$, and from that, calculate the corresponding open-loop response $O(s) = G_s(s) - 1$.
- Transform $G(s)$, (*opt.*) $O(s)$, into time-domain impulse responses; use them as first-order kernels for Volterra systems G (and, optionally, O)

By that, transfer behaviour G and (optionally) disturbance behaviour G_s are specified. Depending on the case, the following sections VI-C1 or VI-C2 can now be used to determine the Volterra controller R (and optionally sensor S). These procedures will then ensure that from the outside, the control loop will behave linearly, even for larger deviations - just as it would in a small range around the operating point, and in accordance with the behaviour of the linearized loop.

1) *Simple Control (Closed-Loop only)*: The controlled unit H and the sensor S need to be known as a Volterra series. The sensor is fixed, and can, for example, incorporate system delay. In the simplest case, S is just the identity system, observing the output and feeding it back without alteration.

Now, the desired closed-loop transfer Volterra system G is specified. Usually, linear behaviour is wanted here, so the first-order kernels will contain the desired impulse response of our closed-loop system. However, nonlinear behaviour can also be set - for example, a slew-rate limitation might be desired, and could be added at this step. Starting from

$$G = HR(J + SHR)^{-1} \quad , \quad (82)$$

with a few steps of basic Volterra algebra, we can calculate the Volterra series for the desired controller R :

$$R = H^{-1}(G^{-1} - S)^{-1} \quad (83)$$

2) *Advanced Control (Closed-Loop and Disturbance)*: The previous example demonstrates how we can design a controller for the desired closed-loop response. If we want some more control over its behaviour, we also might specify the reaction towards an output disturbance (here denoted as G_s). This determines the needed open-loop response O of the system:

$$O = G_s^{-1} - J \quad (84)$$

where J is the identity system.

Of course, we need another degree of freedom now, to fulfill both requirements. We now choose a custom sensor transfer behaviour S , which, together with the controller R , lets us fulfill both the closed-loop transfer target G , and the disturbance target G_s :

$$S = (J - O)G^{-1} \quad , \quad (85)$$

$$R = (SH)^{-1}(O^{-1} - J) \quad , \quad (86)$$

and we have created a controller and sensor according to our specified transfer and disturbance behaviour.

D. Truncation Errors in Control Loops

The terms given so far have always assumed infinite-length and infinite-order Volterra operators. In reality, operators will always be truncated due to restrictions on calculation power. This can both lead to aliasing and time-domain truncation, which will reduce the accuracy of the controller. In this subsection, we briefly want to adress both points.

1) *Aliasing*: When nonlinear terms of order P are present, the input bandwidth B will, due to harmonic generation, result in an output bandwidth of PB . When the sample frequency only fulfills the input nyquist criterium at $2B$, the output bandwidth might still be exceeded for $P > 1$, and output terms will become aliased before they feed back into the system. However, a general guideline [citation] for the creation of discrete-time controllers is to use oversampling in the order of $10 \times$ system bandwidth anyway; in practice, this will result in most input frequencies to be faithfully converted into corresponding output frequencies. Only for very high orders, the aliasing errors will start to play a role. When keeping sufficient safety margin to the maximum input amplitude, those errors can then be neglected.

2) *Finite Impulse Response*: The controllers designed by our proposed method may have a large number of higher-order kernel entries, and thus require much processing power; this might hinder them from being easily implemented. However, one can observe that many real-world examples of nonlinear systems consist of a short-time nonlinearity, surrounded by some linear dynamic systems.

We know the following: If a dynamic system sits in front of a Volterra system, the Volterra system's kernels will get stretched out along the main diagonal; if a linear system is

behind a Volterra system, the overall kernels get stretched out across the directions of all axes. Therefore, by measuring the mean autocorrelation inside all parallels to the main diagonal of higher-order kernels, we can attempt to isolate a linear 'pre' system; by measuring the mean autocorrelation inside all parallels to the axes, we can attempt to isolate a linear 'post' system. This way, we have split up our volterra system into two FIR filters, which can be computed efficiently, and a - hopefully shorter - Volterra system, which requires much less calculation power for similar amounts of truncation error.

E. Two-port systems (MIMO)

The SISO procedure can also be extended towards two-port systems. An ABCD-type amplifier system \mathcal{H} and an ABCD-type feedback system \mathcal{F} form the closed-loop circuit, which has the response:

$$\vec{r}_2 = \mathcal{H}(\mathcal{J} + \mathcal{F}\mathcal{H})^{-1} \vec{r}_1 \quad (87)$$

The feedback system \mathcal{F} samples signal \vec{r}_2 , and adds $\mathcal{F}\vec{r}_2$ to the overall input \vec{r}_1 , so that the modified input \vec{r}_1 into system \mathcal{H} is created:

$$\vec{r}_1 + \mathcal{F}\vec{r}_2 = \vec{r}_1 \quad (88)$$

with \vec{r}_2 being

$$\vec{r}_2 = \mathcal{H}\vec{r}_1 \quad . \quad (89)$$

With some further steps, equation 87 then appears.

The system \mathcal{F} here is thought of not as a physical system, but describes how $(u_2, i_2)^T$ are applied back to the input of the system. In linear two-port feedback theory, systems can be classified into four topologies: series/series, series/shunt, shunt/shunt, and shunt/series. This terminology describes whether a voltage or a current is sampled, and wheter a voltage or a current is added to the input, creating the feedback effect.

We actually do not need to make these distinctions, however; all four cases can be simply incorporated into the operator \mathcal{F} , and even intermediate topologies (the feedback circuit reacts to current AND voltage, and applies current AND voltage to the input) can be modeled. One use case for this would be a source-degenerated (current-sampling, voltage mixing) amplifier with drain-gate feedback (voltage-sampling, current mixing), for example by a resistor or capacitor.

VII. EXAMPLE SYSTEM

TODO: Add a system with feedback, for example a transistor amplifier. Calculate the ABCD-parameters of the transistor with feedback; Compose it with another system, for example of an input matching network.

When finished, convert it to the S-parameter form.

Show in the assembled equation where distortion originates from, and why it grows higher with frequency.

This should demonstrate all possible operations in here, and show how this knowledge can intuitively be applied.

VIII. LIMITATIONS

- Time truncation
- Order truncation
- Weak nonlinearities

IX. CONCLUSION

We have shown that Volterra operators (and the calculus associated with them) allow for a simple notation for the behaviour of nonlinear systems. This notation appears very similar to the one used in complex calculus, which finds widespread application in the analysis of linear electrical networks, once a few mathematical operations are abstracted away.

Consequentially, applying the Volterra operators to nonlinear circuits, we have found that all basic calculations from linear electrical circuit theory can be performed for nonlinear circuits as well. This includes simple examples, like voltage dividers, or parallel-/series-connected impedances; but can also be extended towards multi-port theory (which we have shown at the example of two-ports), and feedback theory. Nonlinear feedback systems that are close to the edge of chaos can even be simulated in this way, although accuracy will be highly dependent on the size of truncation errors.

While Volterra Series are still computationally expensive, for smaller problems they can be calculated on consumer-level hardware. More importantly though, Volterra series give insights into the theoretical understanding of the behaviour of complex nonlinear circuits, as they can be understood as a simple combination of mathematical operators. Volterra series allow for the analytic description of nonlinear dynamic systems - just as complex numbers allow for the analytic description of linear dynamic systems - and can therefore be seen as a natural extension to linear circuit theory. For non-periodic signals, like wideband OFDM, or in data acquisition systems, time-domain Volterra series provide a new option for system characterization.

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X. APPENDIX

A. Two-Port Definitions

In literature, two-port systems are not defined in a standardized manner; they might differ between authors. Therefore, we want to clarify which two-port definitions we have used:

Fig. 19: The port quantity definitions used in our work; a) for field-type systems, and b) for wave-type systems.

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} i_1 \\ u_2 \end{pmatrix} &= \mathcal{G} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix} & \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \end{pmatrix} &= \mathcal{S} \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix} &= \mathcal{H} \begin{pmatrix} i_1 \\ u_2 \end{pmatrix} & \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ a_1 \end{pmatrix} &= \mathcal{T} \begin{pmatrix} a_2 \\ b_2 \end{pmatrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} i_1 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix} &= \mathcal{Y} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{pmatrix} & \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ i_1 \end{pmatrix} &= \mathcal{A} \begin{pmatrix} u_2 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{pmatrix} &= \mathcal{Z} \begin{pmatrix} i_1 \\ i_2 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 20: The ordering of quantities

This ordering allows us to directly compose ABCD-type systems, without having to reverse the direction of the current like it would be needed in some other definitions [cite]. Since this can become especially cumbersome for nonlinear systems, as we would need to introduce another operator for chaining systems, we decided for both currents i_1, i_2 to point in the same direction.

B. ∇ -Y Proof

Here, we are going to prove that the ∇ -Y transformation has no general solution for dynamic nonlinear impedances. Consider the two systems given below. We search for the system Y, which has, given the two node voltages (u_1, u_2) ,

Fig. 21: ∇ -System

Fig. 22: Y-System

the same currents (i_1, i_2) as system ∇ . Our system Y has the impedances Z_a, Z_b, Z_c . The system ∇ is best described by its admittances Y_a, Y_b, Y_c . We can now set up a KVL equation for system ∇ :

$$u_1 = Z_a i_1 + Z_b (i_1 + i_2) \quad (90)$$

and two KCL equations for system Y:

$$i_1 = Y_a u_1 + Y_b (u_1 - u_2) \quad (91)$$

$$i_2 = Y_c u_2 - Y_b (u_1 - u_2) \quad (92)$$

We now set these KCL equations into 90:

$$u_1 = Z_a (Y_a u_1 + Y_b (u_1 - u_2)) + Z_b (Y_a u_1 + Y_c u_2) \quad (93)$$

We now have a look at two specific cases for this equation: a) $u_1 = 0$, b) $u_2 = 0$. This only covers a tiny portion of the equation's domain; so if it turns out that this already yields restrictions on ∇ , they will then be necessary, but might not be sufficient for a transformation to exist.

$$a) \quad 0 = Z_a Y_b (-u_2) + Z_b Y_c u_2 \quad (94)$$

$$b) \quad u_1 = Z_a (Y_a + Y_b) u_1 + Z_b Y_a u_1 \quad (95)$$

For both of them, we can drop the signals (u_1, u_2) and just represent the equations by their operators. We then solve for the operator Z_b :

$$a) \quad Z_b = -Z_a Y_b (-J) Y_c^{-1} \quad (96)$$

$$b) \quad Z_b = (J - Z_a (Y_a + Y_b)) Y_a^{-1} \quad (97)$$

where J is the identity operator.

In both cases, obviously, the equations must be fulfilled by the exact same operator Z_b ; so, we equate the terms:

$$(J - Z_a (Y_a + Y_b)) Y_a^{-1} = -Z_a Y_b (-J) Y_c^{-1} \quad (98)$$

After a few steps, bearing in mind non-commutativity and right-distributivity:

$$Z_a = (Y_a + Y_b)^{-1} + Z_a Y_b (-J) Y_c^{-1} Y_a (Y_a + Y_b)^{-1} \quad (99)$$

Now, we introduce a few assumptions that simplify the following argument. We demand $(Y_a + Y_b)^{-1} = J$, which would just be fulfilled by $Y_a, Y_b = 0.5$ (i.e. they are 2Ω resistors) - our circuit contains two linear and non-dynamic components.

We get:

$$Z_a = J + Z_a (0.5) (-J) Y_c^{-1} (0.5) J \quad (100)$$

This equation has the general form

$$Z = J + ZH \quad (101)$$

Note that H is the operator Y_c enclosed by a few scaling operations and a composition with $-J$, nothing more. This means that it must be minimum phase, and negative overall.

We can now solve it for the 1st order:

$$Z_{(1)} = J + Z_{(1)}H_{(1)} \quad , \quad (102)$$

which can be rearranged for $X_{(1)}$:

$$Z_{(1)} = (J - H_{(1)})^{-1} \quad , \quad (103)$$

so for the first order, we could calculate a value for Z_a , as expected.

For the second order however, we can just set up the following equation:

$$Z_{(2)} = (ZH)_{(2)} \quad , \quad (104)$$

which can be written out as

$$Z_{(2)} = Z_{(1)}H_{(2)} + Z_{(2)}H_{(1)} \quad . \quad (105)$$

Now, we assume that $H_{(2)}$ is a strictly diagonal nonlinearity with $h_2(0,0) \neq 0$. The first summand will thus be a Hammerstein system, which only has Volterra kernel entries along its main diagonal, starting at $(0,0)$.

Its kernels cannot yield values other than 0 for $\tau_1 \neq \tau_2$.

This allows us then to separately investigate the off-diagonal elements, as they must fulfill:

$$Z_{(2)} = Z_{(2)}H_{(1)} \quad \Big|_{\tau_1 \neq \tau_2} \quad . \quad (106)$$

Intuitively, we can already see that this condition might not be possible to fulfill for all possible H . To formally prove this, we first need to discuss some properties of $Z_{(2)}$. Its kernel $z_2(0,0)$ will have a nonzero entry, because: If it had not, the term $Z_{(2)}H_{(1)}$ would also not have one. However, it is guaranteed that the term $Z_{(1)}H_{(2)}$ will, because $Z_{(1)}$ must be minimum-phase and therefore have a nonzero $z_1(0)$ (as it represents the linear part of an impedance); and $h_2(0,0)$, which it is composed with, must also be nonzero, because this was our initial assumption. Their sum must then also contain a nonzero element at this coordinate. To prevent this contradiction, we must conclude that $z_2(0,0)$ indeed needs to be nonzero.

Now, for a specific non-diagonal slice through the kernel ($\tau_2 = 0, \tau_1 \neq 0$), we can write out the composition operation of eq. 106:

$$z_2(\tau_1, 0) = h_1(0) \cdot \sum_{v_1=0}^{\tau_1} z_2(v_1, 0) \cdot h_1(\tau_1 - v_1) \quad \Big|_{\tau_1 \geq 0} \quad (107)$$

This is a simple 1D convolution. This can be solved recursively for $z_2(\tau_1, 0)$:

$$z_2(\tau_1, 0) = \frac{h_1(0)}{1 - h_1^2(0)} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} z_2(\tau_1 - n, 0) \cdot h_1(n) \quad , \quad (108)$$

which, depending on the choice of h_1 , can clearly be diverging (for example for $h_1(0) = -0.9, h_1(1) = -0.4$, which is a valid case given the structure of eq. 100). Therefore, we can say that there are some cases where a converging solution does not exist, and consequently a physical impedance Z_1 cannot be calculated.

If a solution to our assumed problem exists, however, it will only be under the stringent requirement that eq. 108 converges; and quite possibly there are more requirements. Chua's intuition has been right: In the dynamic case, there is indeed no general solution to the ∇ -Y problem; and if there is a solution to a given problem, it might need to follow stringent requirements, for which we have provided one example.

We can conclude that searching for topological simplifications using SISO series is not generally feasible. MIMO series offer a complete description and should be used for solving two-port problems, even when the two-port has a simple structure like the one shown in fig. 21.

C. Some more implications

It should be noted that the impossibility of the ∇ -Y transformation stems directly from some properties of this algebra - namely, that the equation $Z = J + ZH$ has no general solution for all H .

But it seems plausible, at least, that in some cases such solutions might exist; and one could also ask, which other equations might sometimes need to be solved.

For example, consider $XX = H$, where we want to solve for X . One might encounter this equation when stacking two of the same amplifiers - which characteristics would one amplifier then need, in order to achieve some combined transfer operator H ?

A list of similarly interesting equations, their solutions (and whether they exist) could certainly be of value in nonlinear circuit design.

This exact topic has long been discussed for matrix algebra; there, however, we have left- and right-distributivity. Nonlinear systems will pose additional challenges.